

ASSESSMENT OF THE PREDICTORS OF FOOD INSECURITY AMONG RURAL FARMING HOUSEHOLDS IN OGUN STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

This study assessed the predictors of food insecurity among rural farming households in Ogun State, Nigeria. A survey research design was adopted for this study. A multi-stage sampling technique was used to select 150 rural farming households from four Agricultural Development Project zones namely Imeko-Afon, Yewa North, Odeda and Ijebu East Local Government Areas of Ogun State). Data was collected using well-structured questionnaire and analyzed. The results showed that 60.0% of the rural farming households were male, 71.3% were married, 94.7% had formal education. The mean and standard deviation of the age were 42+7.30, household size 5+2.08 persons, farming experience 12+4.27 years, monthly income ₦64,726.07+9,929.71 respectively. Majority 70.0% sourced nutritional information through cell phone, 95.3% radio, 62.7% television, 74.0% friends, 69.3% health workers, 18.7% newspaper and 36.7% internet/email. The negative coefficients for resource allocation indicate that better resource allocation (e.g., income, social, and material resources) significantly reduces food insecurity ($-1.422, p < 0.001$), membership of cooperative ($-1.193, p < 0.031$). Household size ($-0.071, p = 0.002$), farming experience ($0.119, p = 0.015$). This suggests that the models are well-specified and meaningful. Income is highly significant with negative coefficients indicating that higher monthly income significantly reduces food insecurity ($-1.10E-06, p < 0.961$). The study, therefore, recommended that workshops, seminars for rural farming households and partnerships with agricultural extension services to provide practical training and formulation of policy that supports food security. The cooperative societies should also be supported with funds and access to markets to enhance their effectiveness in improving food security.

Keywords: Food insecurity, household, resources, nutrition

INTRODUCTION

Food insecurity is defined as the state of lacking regular access to enough safe and nutritious food for normal growth and development and an active and healthy life (Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), 2022). Severe food insecurity sets in when people run out of food for days, experience hunger and, at the most extreme, gone for

days without eating, putting their health and well-being at grave risk, based on the Food Insecurity Experience Scale (Odusina *et al.*, 2017). It therefore refers to a lack of consistent access to food, which diminishes dietary quality, disrupts normal eating patterns, and can have negative consequences for nutrition, health and well-being (Fadare *et al.*, 2019).

The determinants of food insecurity can be broadly categorized into social, economic, environmental, political and physical factors. Countries have become more food insecure as a result of factors such as: droughts, land degradation, population explosion, lack of productive resources, insufficient assets, poverty and deprivation (Farzana et al., 2017). Food insecurity has been and remained a public health threat that needs to be addressed in order to reduce environmental hazards and problems of malnutrition, dietary diversity needs and psychological dysfunction (Endale et al., 2019). Studies on determinants of food security have been conducted across the world and they range from socio-economic, institutional, environmental, and safety-related perspectives. Improved nutrition is thought to have a multiplier effect across the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) (World Food Programme, 2023). Yet, much like other low- and middle-income countries, achieving the SDGs in Nigeria is challenged by co-existence of under nutrition, micronutrient deficiencies, and growing rates of overweight and obesity in the population. This implies there is potential to nudge consumer behavior towards healthier and sustainable diets and address nutritional challenges through changes in the food systems. Identifying entry points for interventions requires understanding of the link between dietary consumption and the components of the existing food systems (Horton, 2019). Previous studies suggested that sources of nutritional information help people to be nutrition-sensitive and food-based approaches towards multiple forms of malnutrition are effective, sustainable, and long-term solutions (Blake, 2021; Barrett, 2019).

Household resource allocation is the

assignment of available resources to various uses. In the context of an entire economy, resources can be allocated by various means, such as markets, or planning. Household resource allocation or resource management is the scheduling of activities and the resources required by those activities while taking into consideration both the resource availability and the project time (FAO, 2022). Household resource allocation and food security are inter-related and this to be able to access, afford, and source adequate foodstuffs. According to the United Nations Committee on World Food Security, food security is defined as meaning that all people, at all times, have physical, social, and economic access to sufficient, safe, and nutritious food that meets their food preferences and dietary needs for an active and healthy life. The availability of food irrespective of class, gender or region is another element of food security. Recently, Nigeria made some progress in the area of per capital daily calorie intake and the proportion of under nourished people. The average national per capital daily calorie intake increased from 2050 to 2700 kcal in 2019-2020 (FAO, 2021). Thus, this study assessed food insecurity, nutritional information and household resource allocation among rural farming households in Ogun State, Nigeria. The objectives of this study are to identify sources of nutritional information in the study area and also identify the determinants of food insecurity among rural farming households in the study area.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area

The study was conducted in Ogun State.

The state is located in Southwestern Nigeria, Ogun State covers 16,762 square kilometres. It borders Lagos State to the south, Oyo and Osun states to the North, Ondo State to the east and the Republic of Benin to the west. Agriculture is one of the primary occupations of the people in the State. Ogun State is endowed with natural resources which include extensive fertile soil suitable for agriculture and mineral deposits. The climate and soil of the state are suitable for the cultivation of a wide range of food crops which include rice, maize, cassava, yam and banana and cash crops which include cocoa, kolanut, rubber, palm oil and palm kernels. Ogun State is one of the largest producers of kolanut, timber, rubber and ofada rice on a large scale. There are twenty (20) Local Government Areas (LGAs) in the state and Ogun State Agricultural Development Project (OGADEP) is sub-divided into four (4) agricultural zones namely Abeokuta, Ijebu-Ode, Ikenne and Ilaro (Ogun State Diary, 2024).

Data collection and sampling procedure

A well-structured questionnaire and oral interviews were used to elicit information from rural farming households in Ogun State while multi-stage sampling technique was used to select 150 respondents. Firstly, the State was stratified into its four Agricultural Development Project zones. The second stage involved the purposive selection of four LGAs notable for crop production based on reconnaissance survey information. Imeko-afon, Yewa North, Odeda and Ijebu East Local Government Areas were selected. In the third stage, proportionate sampling technique was employed to select 30% respondents each from the lists of registered rural farming households in four sampled Local Government Areas. On sources of nutritional information, respondents were asked to indicate the sources of nutritional

information such as; cell phone, radio, television, newspaper, friends/neighbours, health officers, internet/email, and social association and extension agents. They were asked to add other options not listed. This was measured on a yes or no scale and was assigned scores of 1 and 0 respectively. Individual means of the sources of nutritional information was found and used to rank them. On incidence of food insecurity among the respondents was calculated by using Food Insecurity Index. Food Insecurity Experience Scale (FIES) was used to measure food insecurity status among rural farming households. The FIES Survey Module (FIES-SM) consists of eight questions regarding people's access to adequate food and can be easily integrated into various types of population surveys will be adopted for this study.

Data analysis

Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics such as frequency counts; percentage, mean and standard deviation were used to describe the socio-economic characteristics of rural farming households while inferential statistics such as ordered logit regression was used to determine food insecurity, nutritional information and household resource allocation pattern among rural farming households. The core formula for an ordered logit model relates the cumulative probability of an outcome to a linear predictor through the logit function. Specifically, for a dependent variable with C categories, the cumulative probability $g_{ci} = \Pr(Y_i \leq c | x_i)$ is related to a linear predictor $\beta'x_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x_{1i} + \beta_2 x_{2i} + \dots$ by the logit function. Where, Y is the dependent variable which represents the predictor of food insecurity among rural farming households in the study area, and $X_1 - X_{10}$ are the independent variables and are denoted as follows:

X_1 = Age of rural farming households, X_2 = Sex, X_3 = Marital status, X_4 = Education, X_5 = Household size, X_6 =

Farming experience, X_7 = Income, X_8 = Extension contact, X_9 = Cooperative members, X_{10} = Resource allocation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Determination of the socio-economic characteristics of the rural farming households in the study area

Results on Table 1 reveal the socioeconomic distribution of the rural farming households in Southwestern Nigeria. The age distribution of the rural farming households reveals that the majority (50%) of the farming households in Ogun State. The mean age of the rural households was 42 ± 7.3 years. The implication of the result is that the majority of the rural household heads in Ogun State, Nigeria are still young and within their productive age. This suggests that these households have the physical capacity to engage in labor-intensive farming activities, potentially enhancing agricultural productivity if the necessary resources, such as inputs, training, and technology, are effectively allocated. The majority (71.3) of the household heads was male in the study area. The implication is that married individuals dominated the rural household heads when compared to their unmarried counterparts. Married individuals are more likely to head households due to the traditional societal expectations of married men or women being responsible for their families' economic well-being. Married individuals are more likely to allocate resources towards maintaining household stability and ensuring the welfare of their family members. The majority (49.3%) of the household heads had secondary education. This implies that the majority of the household heads are educated and this may have an implication on their level of adoption of innovative practices in farm production as adaption capacity of an individual depends on their level of their education and exposure. The average household size was 5 ± 2.08

persons. The implication is that the majority of the farming household heads have ample experience about farming and this may have a positive influence on their decision to cope with food insecurity and utilize their resources well to obtain better output. The average monthly income was $\text{₦}64,726.67 \pm 9929.717$. The implication is that most of the rural farming household heads realized a fair income from the enterprise and this may have a positive influence on their resource allocation pattern, coping strategy and food security status. This result supports the finding of Belachew (2022) on food security, food based coping strategies and suboptimal dietary practices of adolescents in Jimma zone southwest Ethiopia who found out that food security can be achieved if food wastages through processing and storage are minimized or stopped.

The result reveals that the majority (72.7%) of the rural farming household heads opined that extension agents visit them occasionally. This implies that extension visitations in the areas are not frequent and this may have a negative influence on the adoption of innovative practices and overall food security in these rural areas that will result to better output among the farming households. The majority (77.3%) of the rural farming household heads are members of a cooperative association. The implication is that most of the household heads are members of a cooperative association and this may have a positive influence on the amount of fund available to the household, as the cooperative association influences the ability of the households to pool their resources to enjoy high economies of scale. This would therefore enhance their food security status. This result is in agreement with the findings of Barret (2019) on food security measurement in a global context, who found out those farmers who belong to various cooperative societies hardly run out of food or money.

Table 1: Socio-economic characteristics of the respondents (n=150)

Variables	Frequency	Percentage	Mean	SD
Age (years)			42	7.30
< 40	65	43.3		
41 - 50	75	50.0		
51 – 60	10	6.7		
Sex				
Male	90	60.0		
Female	60	40.0		
Marital status				
Single	10	6.7		
Married	107	71.3		
Separated	12	8.0		
Divorced	16	10.7		
Widowed	5	3.3		
Educational status (years)				
No Formal	8	5.3		
Primary	24	16.0		
Secondary	75	50.0		
Tertiary	43	28.7		
Household size (persons)			5	2.08
1 - 4	65	43.3		
5 - 8	75	50.0		
9 - 12	10	6.7		
Farming experience (years)			12	4.27
1 - 10	42	28.0		
11 - 20	101	67.3		
21 - 30	7	4.7		
Monthly Income (₦)			64,726.07	9,929.71
0 - 20,000	1	0.7		
20,001 - 40,000	-	-		
40,001 - 60,000	76	50.6		
60,001 – 80,000	66	44.0		
> 80,001	7	4.7		
Membership of cooperative				
Yes	116	22.7		
No	34	77.3		
Extension contact				
Regularly	14	9.3		
Occasionally	109	72.7		
Never	27	18.0		

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Identification of sources of nutritional information in the study area

The result shows that the majority of rural farming households obtained nutritional information via cell phone (70.0%), radio (95.3%), television (62.7%), friends/neighbour (74.0%) and health officers/workers (69.3%) while some educated rural farming households among them obtained their nutritional information also via newspaper (18.7%) and internet/email (36.7%) respectively. The findings on the sources of nutritional information have a significant implication for food security. More so, the high reliance on mobile phones and radios for accessing nutritional information suggests that these households are well-positioned to receive timely and accurate advice on food

selection, preparation, and dietary diversity. The widespread use of mobile phones (70.0%) and radios (95.3%) as trusted sources also means that there is potential for impactful behavioral change within these communities. Public health campaigns and educational programs can leverage these platforms to spread messages about nutrition, food hygiene, and balanced diets. When households are well-informed, they can prevent food-related illnesses and malnutrition, which are common in food-insecure environments. This result corroborates with the findings of Chung et al. (2020) who found out that radio and health centres are common sources of nutritional information to rural dwellers and highly educated among them also serve as alternative sources.

Table 2: Distribution of sources of nutritional information among rural farming household in Ogun State (n=150)

Items	Yes	No
1. Cell phone	105 (70.0)	45 (30.0)
2. Radio	143 (95.3)	7 (4.7)
3. Television	94 (62.7)	56 (37.3)
4. Newspaper	28 (18.7)	122 (81.3)
5. Friends/Neighbour	111 (74.0)	39 (26.0)
6. Health officer/workers	104 (69.3)	46 (30.7)
7. Internet/Email	55 (36.7)	95 (63.3)

Source: Field Survey, 2024.

Objective 3: To identify the determinants of food insecurity among rural farming households in Ogun State, Nigeria

Result shown in Table 3 reveals the factors influencing food insecurity among rural farming households in Ogun State, Nigeria. The Likelihood Ratio (LR) chi-squared values are highly significant ($p < 0.001$) across all models, indicating that the independent variables collectively contribute to explaining the variations in food insecurity status in each state and the pooled sample. This suggests that the

models are well-specified and meaningful. The log-likelihood values across all models are relatively close, suggesting that the models are similarly effective in predicting food insecurity status. The cut values (/cut1, /cut2, /cut3) represent the thresholds between the different categories of food insecurity: food secure, mildly food insecure, moderately food insecure, and severely food insecure. These cut values help define the points at which the likelihood of moving from one category to the next changes. The household size has a

significant negative impact on food security (-0.071, $p = 0.002$), indicating that larger households are more prone to food insecurity, likely due to higher consumption needs. The implication is that larger households in Ogun State are more likely to experience food insecurity, likely due to higher consumption needs without a proportionate increase in income. Farming experience is significant (0.119, $p = 0.015$), with more experienced farmers being less food insecure. This result highlights the importance of experience in improving agricultural productivity and food access. The implication is that more experienced farmers tend to be less food insecure, as they likely have better skills in crop management, resource allocation, and risk mitigation. Agricultural extension services should prioritize experience-based mentorship programs where experienced farmers mentor younger or less experienced farmers, thereby increasing overall food security. Membership in cooperatives significantly reduces food insecurity (-1.193, $p = 0.031$). This underscores the importance of social networks and cooperative structures in providing households with access to resources, credit, and support systems that enhance food security. The implication is that being a member of a cooperative reduces food insecurity, as cooperatives

often provide access to credit, shared resources, and knowledge transfer. Encouraging cooperative formation and ensuring their sustainability could be a crucial strategy to combat food insecurity. Governments and Non-Governmental Organizations should invest in cooperative capacity building and provide support through loans, grants, and training (Belachew, 2022; Hatloy, 2020).

The negative coefficients for resource allocation (-1.422, $p = 0.001$) indicate that better resource allocation (e.g., income, social, and material resources) significantly reduces food insecurity. This highlights the role of efficient management of household resources in improving food security. The implication is that better resource allocation—whether financial, material, or social—greatly reduces food insecurity. Efficient resource management enables households to make optimal use of available assets and avoid wastage. These results corroborate with the findings of Hatloy (2020) and Desai (2021), who found out that rural farming households are at a greater risk of falling into severe food insecurity if exposed to additional shocks, such as high food prices, poor harvests, or illness.

Table 4: Ordered logit regression analysis on the determinants of food insecurity among rural farming households in Ogun State, Nigeria

Variables	Coefficient	P>Z
Age	-0.003	0.922
Sex	-0.045	0.903
Marital status	0.272	0.483
Education	0.014	0.707
Household size	-0.071	0.002
Farming experience	0.119	0.015
Income	-1.01E-06	0.961
Extension contact	-0.235	0.464
Cooperative members	-1.193**	0.031
Resource allocation	-1.422***	0.001
Cut1	-5.469	
Cut2	-3.796	
Cut3	-0.470	
LR Chi ²	57.17***	
Prob > Chi ²	0.000***	
Observations	150.00	
Pseudo R ²	0.1635	
Log likelihood	-146.285	

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Note: Significant at *** 1%, ** 5% level of probability

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the exploration of rural farming households in Ogun State Nigeria reveals a profound connection between food insecurity, nutritional information and household resource allocation, and the determinants of food security. Effective resource management emerges as a pivotal factor in shaping food security outcomes, with households that strategically allocate their income, social support, and material resources demonstrating better resilience against food shortages. The analysis underscores that socioeconomic characteristics, including education, household size, income, and farming experience, significantly influence food insecurity levels. Investing in social networks and cooperative structures can

also bolster households' resilience, providing them with essential support during times of crisis. Ultimately, addressing the determinants of food security through improved resource allocation and effective coping strategies will be crucial for fostering long-term food security and enhancing the livelihoods of rural farming households in Southwestern Nigeria. The study, therefore, recommended that workshops, seminars for rural farming households and partnerships with agricultural extension services to provide practical training and formulation of policy that supports food security. The cooperative societies should also be supported with funds and access to markets to enhance their effectiveness in improving food security.

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